

Simple Hydrothermal Method for One – Dimensional Synthesis of Al-doped ZnO for an Organic Dye-Based DSSC Application

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Abstract: Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorods are promising photoanode materials for dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) due to their high electron mobility, favorable aspect ratio, and tunable optoelectronic properties. In this study, vertically aligned ZnO nanorods were hydrothermally grown on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates and doped with Al³⁺ (1–7 at%) to optimize charge transport. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed successful Al³⁺ incorporation, evidenced by a slight peak shift, while retaining the hexagonal wurtzite structure. The nanorods exhibited controlled morphologies, with diameters ranging from 78 to 141 nm and aspect ratios varying between 13% and 37%. Optical characterization revealed that sensitization with D205 dye extended light absorption into the visible spectrum, significantly improving photon harvesting. Among the tested dopant concentrations, the 1% Al³⁺-doped ZnO (AZO-1%) photoanode demonstrated optimal performance, achieving a short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) of 25.7 mA/cm² and a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 4.15%. These results highlight the synergistic effects of Al³⁺ doping and nanostructural engineering in enhancing DSSC performance through improved charge collection and reduced recombination.

Keywords: Al-doped; dye sensitized solar cell; hydrothermal; nanorods; Zinc Oxide

1. Introduction

The use of solar energy and associated conversion technology presents a sustainable and visually appealing solution to meet growing global energy demands. Among the most promising methods for harnessing solar power is photovoltaic energy conversion, particularly through dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). These cells offer a cost-effective, flexible, and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional silicon-based solar panels, making them a key innovation in renewable energy technology¹. DSSCs have reached a peak conversion efficiency of 12.3%, which is still lower than that of silicon-based solar cells².

A DSSCs is an advanced third-generation photovoltaic device known for its efficient charge transfer and high performance. As a photoelectrochemical system utilizing metal oxides and organic dyes, DSSCs offer promising solutions to energy and environmental challenges. The key components—photoanode, electrolyte, and counter electrode—are critical in determining the cell's efficiency. Typically, the photoanode consists of a metal oxide, which plays a vital role by anchoring dye molecules and facilitating electron transfer to the external circuit. For optimal energy conversion, DSSCs require effective electron transport to minimize charge recombination, significantly enhancing overall performance³. TiO₂-based photoanodes, including nanoparticles, nanoporous

structures, and nanocrystals, are the most commonly used in DSSCs. However, their widespread application faces limitations due to issues such as rapid charge recombination and low electron transport efficiency⁴). ZnO, with its superior electron transport properties compared to other metal oxides, presents a viable solution to these challenges. Its high electron mobility not only enhances photocurrent density but also helps reduce the rapid recombination rate observed in TiO₂-based systems⁵).

ZnO is an II-VI semiconductor type with an exciton binding energy of around 60 meV at ambient temperature⁶). ZnO serves as a promising alternative to TiO₂ in photoanode applications due to its abundant availability, strong photosensitivity, non-toxic nature, and simple synthesis process. Among various ZnO nanostructures, nanorods (NRs) stand out for their ability to enhance DSSC performance. Their superior electron transport and light-harvesting properties contribute to an energy conversion efficiency of approximately 1.65%⁷). Experimental studies demonstrate that precise control of ZnO nanorod aspect ratios (length-to-diameter) can optimize both photoelectrode performance metrics: dye loading capacity and charge carrier diffusion lengths. Furthermore, strategic morphological tuning of nanorod dimensions and geometry offers an alternative pathway to achieve these photovoltaic enhancements^{8,9}). To optimize ZnO nanorod properties (particularly electrical conductivity), structural modifications are essential. Incorporating n-type dopants (Al, Ga, In) becomes necessary when density functional theory (DFT) analysis reveals that residual hydrogen impurities may introduce donor levels and cause Zn site displacements within the ZnO crystal lattice¹⁰).

One of the n-type dopings that may be applied to ZnO is aluminum (Al). The purpose of adding Al to ZnO is to raise the concentration of charge carriers, which should improve DSSC efficiency and conductivity¹¹). Furthermore, the optical band gap of ZnO may be shifted by doping into the visible light range, which is important for solar cell applications¹²). Excessive Al doping concentration causes not only a change in the absorbance component but also an increase in the band gap¹²). The best performance of ZnO with Al doping is about 3.96%¹³). Furthermore, because of its smaller ionic radius (Al = 0.054 nm and Zn = 0.074 nm), Al³⁺ may be able to replace Zn²⁺ in the crystal lattice. The optical band gap of the undoped ZnO nanoparticles is around 3.37 eV¹⁴).

NRs arrangements were used to create the Al-doped ZnO texture layer. The formation of this texture layer starts with coating the conductive glass through a cheap and easy spin coating method¹⁵). The hydrothermal method is one of the methods that is employed, and it is beneficial due to its low cost and low growth temperature¹⁶). The growth of aligned ZnO NRs arrays has been demonstrated to be facilitated by this approach, which has been thoroughly examined and adjusted for several factors, including pH, temperature,

seed coat quality, and solution concentration. It was difficult, therefore, to get precisely aligned ZnO NRs doped with group III ions.

The goal of this work is to maximize the hydrothermal technique to obtain a high aspect ratio and well-organized Al-doped ZnO NRs for the DSSC photoanode.

2. Experimental Method

2.1. Procedure

First, FTO-Glass was cut with dimensions of 1.0 cm × 1.0 cm and 1.5 cm × 2.5 cm. The 1.0 cm × 1.0 cm FTO-glass was used to characterize its structure and optical properties, while the 1.5 cm × 2.5 cm FTO-glass was used to characterize the electrical properties of the DSSC cell. The FTO-glass was then washed using ultrasonic using soapy water, deionized (DI) water, and acetone, respectively. The duration of each washing was 15 minutes and then dried. Zinc acetate dihydrate was dissolved in isopropanol to a concentration of 0.5 M. Using a spin coater, the solution was deposited on FTO-glass at 2000 rpm for 1 minute to form a ZnO seed layer. The spin coating process was then followed by heating at 100°C for 15 minutes. After that, the spin coating process was repeated twice. Heating at 100°C for 15 minutes was then followed by gradual heating at 300°C for 15 minutes and heating at 500°C for 30 minutes. Another FTO-Glass substrate was also prepared like the steps previously described, but using a solution with the addition of Al nitrate non hydrate as much as 1 at%, 3 at%, 5 at%, and 7 at%.

Then the nanorods were grown via the hydrothermal method. 0.05 M zinc nitrate hexahydrate and 0.25 hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) were dissolved in DI water. This solution was stirred for 45 min at room temperature and then mixed through stirring for 15 min. Then, the resulting solution was poured on a crucible. Samples were then immersed in a 45° tilted position with the seed layer facing downwards. The crucible was then placed in an oven at 90°C for 6 hours. After the hydrothermal reaction, the samples were then rinsed using DI water to remove the residue. Finally, the samples were dried at 450°C to improve the crystallinity and orientation of the ZnO NRs.

2.2. Characterization

These samples were then characterized to determine their structure, morphology, optical properties, and electrical properties as applications in DSSCs. Structural characterization was performed by an X-ray diffraction (XRD) PANalytical X'Pert Pro system using a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 0.1541$ nm) operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. The 2θ range is 10°-60°. Scanning electron microscopy, or SEM (FEI Inspect-S50), was used to observe the formation of ZnO NRs formed after the hydrothermal process. Absorbance spectra were tested

using an Analytik Jena Specord 200 plus UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

2.3. Electrical Performances

Furthermore, this thin layer part was used as a photoanode in the DSSC system and tested using an I-V meter (Keithley 6517B) under 1 sun illumination using a solar simulator (ABET Technology Model 10500). The DSSC was fabricated into one cell system in the order of photoanode, dye, electrolyte, and counter electrode, as shown in Figure 1. The dye used was 0.7 mM organic dye D205 dissolved in acetonitrile (Solaronix). Before fabrication, organic dye loading was carried out on the photoanode through immersion for 24 hours. The photoanode and the counter electrode were then joined through a sealing process using a thermoplastic sealing film made from Surlyn (Meltonix 1170-25, Solaronix). Electrolyte injection was then carried out under vacuum conditions. The electrolyte used was an iodide-based liquid electrolyte (Mosalyte TDE-250, Solaronix).

Fig. 1: DSSC fabrication

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Crystal Structure

Doping can modify the n-type semiconductor behavior caused by intrinsic defects in ZnO, a property that has drawn a lot of interest for both basic and practical¹⁷. Intrinsic defects consist of interstitial zinc (Zn_i) and oxygen vacancies (V_O) as donors, and zinc vacancies (V_{Zn}) and interstitial oxygen (O_i) as acceptors¹⁸. Zn_i is a shallow donor with a low formation energy, which supports the claims made in certain publications that Zn_i defects account for the n-type behaviour. Low formation energy is necessary for V_O defects, but their contribution to n-type conductivity is constrained by the deep donor feature. When it comes to acceptor defects, V_{Zn} and O_i often develop at grain boundaries and stable at higher oxygen partial pressures. This can impede electronic transport and reduce electrical conductivity¹⁷. Therefore, the electrical performance of n-type ZnO materials is closely related to their microstructure. The crystal structure, sample composition, peak intensity, peak shift, and peak broadening of a material, like Al on ZnO, will all be impacted by the doping treatment.

Figure 2 presents the diffractogram of ZnO NRs which it can be inferred that they all belong to the same phase—the ZnO wurtzite structure. A more thorough examination reveals that they are all characterized by a single, extremely bright peak in the hkl (002) plane, or at the Bragg position between 34.20° and 34.70° . It is hypothesized that the hydrothermal process produces homogenous and preferred orientation of nanorods that develop in the c-axis direction with the same crystal shape. The absence of Al peaks indicates that Al atoms successfully substituting in the ZnO lattice and do not lead to the formation of new phases^{19,20}.

Fig. 2: Diffractograms of AZO NRs

Al^{3+} doping on ZnO causes changes in peak intensity, peak shift, and peak broadening. On the (002) crystal plane, it shifts towards a higher 2θ , commonly called a blue peak shift. The blue shift attributes to an increase in interatomic distances or changes in electronic properties that will be affected to their charge transfer and molecular interactions²¹. But AZO-1% shows the opposite. The bragg position (002) shifts towards the left or can be referred to as a red shift. The red shift typically indicates a decrease in interatomic distances and associated with increased disorder or structural changes in materials²². This can occur due to a change in the lattice parameter, which is reflected by the peak position, as shown in Figure 3.

The intensity in the samples increases as the doping concentration increases; this corresponds to the possibility of defects or changes in electron density and exhibit higher crystallinity of the NRs structure²¹. This can occur because the radius of Al^{3+} ions have a smaller size than the radius of Zn^{2+} ions in ZnO. It is known that the radius of Al^{3+} ions is 0.053 nm, while the radius of Zn^{2+} ions is 0.074 nm¹⁴. Table 1 shows the structural parameters of AZO. The lattice constant symbolized by c of the wurtzite structure of both ZnO and AZO is calculated using the equation²³:

Fig. 3: Bragg position of (002) AZO NRs

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{\sin \theta} \tag{1}$$

where $\lambda = 0.15406$ nm which is the wavelength of the X-Ray and θ is the Bragg position. This lattice constant is then used to calculate the internal strain ϵ_z of the nanorods using the equation²⁴:

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{c - c_0}{c_0} \times 100\% \tag{2}$$

where c_0 is equal to 0.5206 nm, the conventional lattice constant for unstrained ZnO NRs²⁵. A positive strain indicates tensile strain, which is an expansion of the lattice constant. The lattice constantly contracts when there is compressive strain, as indicated by a negative strain. Using the following equation, one may determine the biaxial strain present in NRs using this internal strain²⁶:

$$\sigma = -233 \frac{(c - c_0)}{c_0} = -203\epsilon \text{ GPa} \tag{3}$$

Compressive strain on Al doped ZnO NR indicates a reduction of the unit cell dimension and the crystal size is reduced when compared to its balanced state. This strain will affect the optical and electronic characteristics of the material²⁷. The original defect in ZnO shows the presence of oxygen vacancy which has a lower formation energy than other defects such as metal doping elements, so there should be more ZnO_{1-x} unit cells. This is indicated by the positive value in the biaxial strain where the oxygen vacancy causes c_{002} to be higher than the standard c_0 . The biaxial strain on the sample shows a very strong residual stress along the surface of the sample layer which is indicated by the negative internal strain and affected the AZO-1% (002) peak shifting to the left. The high residual stress in the sample indicates a relatively low cavity density. This is a consequence of the unbalanced film deposition and the incorporation of Al doping atoms in ZnO, which provides the driving force so that the atomic flux is at the boundary of the nanorods and will affect the

energy gap. Changes of the lattice constant in each sample will affect the size of the crystal that varies. The crystal size D is then calculated using the Scherrer equation²⁸:

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \tag{4}$$

with D the crystal size, β is the FWHM possessed by the reflection plane (002), θ is the Bragg diffraction angle, λ is the x-ray wavelength, which is 1.5418 Å, and k represents the Scherrer constant (0.98). The crystal sizes are then presented in Table 1. The highest crystal size is owned by AZO - 3% sample which is 65.167 nm, where this result is double that of the usual 30-36 nm²⁹.

Table 1: Structural parameters of AZO NRs

Sample	(002) position (°)	FWHM (°)	c-axis (nm)	Strain (%)	σ (GPa)
ZnO	34.457	0.143	0.520	-0.086	58.306
AZO - 1%	34.381	0.156	0.521	0.012	53.276
AZO - 3%	34.392	0.127	0.521	0,096	65.167
AZO - 5%	34.421	0.171	0.520	0.014	48.732
AZO - 7%	34.419	0.171	0.520	0.020	48.746

3.2. Nanorods Morphology

Figure 4 shows the SEM top views of five samples from ZnO to AZO-7% with 100,000× magnification. The top views of the samples show a hexagonal-like shape. As the addition of Al at% increases, the hexagonal shape formed becomes larger. At the highest concentration, at AZO-7%, there are some hexagonal that are formed with other hexagonal. It can be assumed that there is not too much difference between doped and undoped; everything still has the same shape and only differs in size. This uniform shape can still facilitate stable charge movement and can help the dye to optimize light absorption for energy conversion³⁰. What changes here is the geometry of the nanorods, which changes during the crystallization process. This behaviour is related to the energy level of certain crystal surfaces, where the surface with the highest energy wants to minimize surface exposure to minimize energy so that it will affect the diameter size of the hexagonal cross section of the nanorod²⁶. This is thought to be a result of the addition of Al to the seed layer.

Fig. 4: Top view of SEM AZO NRs on FTO-glass

Figure 5 shows the cross section of ZnO and AZO on FTO substrate using atomic doping concentrations of (a) 0%, (b) 1%, (c) 3%, (d) 5%, and (e) 7% with 20,000 \times magnification. For samples (a) to (e), the NRs formed are vertically aligned in the c-axis direction. Hydrothermal NRs growth with different doping concentrations resulted in different layer thicknesses, which are in the range of 1.041 to 2.953 μm , in details resumed in Table 2. The cross-sectional diameter of the NRs formed was measured between 78 and 141 nm. This causes the aspect ratio of this thin layer to be high. The aspect ratio is obtained through the comparison of the length and diameter of the NRs. The length of the NRs is obtained through the layer thickness of the ZnO film. The addition of Al doping to ZnO shows a very fluctuating influence on the aspect ratio of the thin film produced that ensured a porous morphology and maintenance of the surface area for dye adsorption³¹.

Fig. 5: SEM cross section of AZO NRs

Table 2: Morphology parameter of AZO NRs

Sample	Hexagonal diameter (nm)	Film Thickness (μm)	Aspect Ratio
ZnO	119	2.682	22.537
AZO – 1%	79	1.041	13.177
AZO – 3%	78	2.953	37.858
AZO – 5%	127	2.381	18.748
AZO – 7%	141	1.904	13.503

3.3. Optical Properties

Figure 6 shows the absorbance spectra of ZnO and AZO on the FTO-glass substrate in the wavelength range of 200–800 nm. From all samples, there is one maximum

absorbance peak at a wavelength of about 350 nm near the edge of the exciton absorbance region band in the ultraviolet region. This absorbance peak is smaller than the existing reference, which is around 380 nm⁶). As the concentration of Al addition to ZnO increases, the absorbance area decreases. This can be correlated with the semiconductor properties of thin films that absorb ultraviolet radiation and transmit visible light³²). Next, the maximum absorption region of the AZO layer is at a wavelength of <355 nm, while the other is a strong transmittance region at >500 nm. The expansion of the absorption wavelength range can be facilitated by organic dye that enables a broader absorption of visible light. This broader absorption range further enhances the PCE of DSSCs³³).

Fig. 6: Absorbance spectrum and energy gap of AZO NRs

The transmittance region is also referred to as the absorption edge³⁴). The absorption edge indicates the transition from valence to conduction band. Furthermore, from these absorbance results, an energy band gap can be found that can evaluate the electronic properties of the semiconductor and dye for effective light harvesting³⁵). This energy band gap is obtained through the Tauc

equation for the direct energy gap, as shown below³⁶⁾:

$$(ah\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g) \tag{5}$$

In this equation, we have used the values of $n = 2$ for a direct transition to determine the optical gap of ZnO as it is proposed to be a direct band gap material. Using Tauc fitting, we have obtained experimental energy gap of ZnO and AZO NRs is around 3.0 eV. With the energy gap obtained by ZnO, it is considered impossible to be applied as a DSSC because the energy gap is not in the visible light wave. Thus, the addition of dye here must also pay attention to the energy gap of the dye to be used.

Organic dyes are often chosen as dyes in ZnO-based DSSCs because of their compatibility with strong adsorption, which is very effective in assisting electron transfer³⁷⁾. Dye D205 with a D-A- π -A structure, has an energy gap around 1.89 - 2.10 eV, which can support ZnO-based DSSCs to have absorption in visible light³⁸⁾. The smallest energy gap of AZO-1% is related to the length of the nanorods produced where the result is directly proportional³⁹⁾.

3.4. Electrical Properties

The fabricated DSSCs were examined using electrochemically with a solar illumination light intensity of 100 mW/cm². The J-V profiles of DSSCs were employed to obtain the photovoltaic parameters for example short circuit current density (J_{sc}), open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), fill factor (FF), power maximum (P_{max}) and conversion efficiency (η). The efficiency (η) and FF were obtained from the below equations⁴⁰⁾:

$$FF = J_{max} \times V_{max} / J_{sc} \times V_{oc} \tag{1}$$

$$\eta(\%) = J_{sc} \times V_{oc} \times FF / I_{ins} \times 100 \tag{2}$$

Table 3: Photovoltaic parameter of AZO NRs

Sample	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	FF	η (%)
ZnO	9.96	0.44	0.38	1.64
AZO - 1%	25.7	0.51	0.31	4.15
AZO - 3%	7.96	0.35	0.34	0.95
AZO - 5%	3.05	0.34	0.34	0.35
AZO - 7%	5.18	0.44	0.34	0.77

Note: active cell area = 0.25 cm² and tests for 1 cell.

DSSC devices composed of ZnO and Al-doped ZnO photoanodes at different concentrations of 1, 3, 5, and 7 at% and using organic dye D205 as sensitizer and photoelectrochemical parameters were measured using Keithley 6517B I-V meter under 100 mW/cm² Xe Arc light source, with an active area of 0.5×0.5 cm². Figure 5 shows the VOC-JSC relationship, and the photovoltaic parameters and solar cell efficiency of various concentrations are summarized in Table 3. J_{sc} represent the current density in the range of 3.05 to 25.7 mA/cm². This indicates the maximum current that can produce by

the cell under the illumination⁴¹⁾. J_{sc} requires that the electrons successfully transport to the electrode without recombination at the dye/photoanode/electrolyte interface⁴²⁾. Figure 7 shows a correlation between VOC and J_{sc} . The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) changes in the range of 0.344 V to 0.512 V. The efficiency of the ZnO device is 1.64% as shown in Figure 5. The comparison between photovoltaic devices ZnO NRs – based is written in the Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of photovoltaic parameters of present work with reported works

Photoanode	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	FF	η (%)	[Ref.]
Bare ZnO-NR	3.31	0.57	0.48	1.06	1)
ZnO	9.96	0.44	0.38	1.64	PW
Ca-doped ZnO	5.3	0.63	0.36	1.20	43)
Sr-doped ZnO	1.54	0.79	0.68	0.84	44)
B-doped ZnO	2.23	0.48	0.36	0.41	45)
AZO - 1%	25.7	0.51	0.31	4.15	PW

AZO-1% has different structural characteristics from the others, where the lattice parameters expand, which can affect its optical and electrical properties²²⁾. AZO-1% tends to have the highest area and absorbance intensity among others, proving that the absorption of photons carried out by AZO-1% has the best absorption power. Good absorption of photons in the organic dye on AZO-1% thin film will lead to fast electron transfer because of the aggregation between dye molecules on the surface of AZO-1% which will affect several DSSC performance parameters, such as J_{sc} and V_{oc} and hindering the efficient injection of electrons into the AZO layer⁴⁶⁾

Fig. 7: J_{sc} - V_{oc} of AZO NRs

For AZO-1%, the Nyquist plot and matching equivalent circuit are shown on Figure 8. The charge transfer resistance (R_1) correlated to the Pt counter electrode and electrolyte (Pt/electrolyte) is shown by the tiny semicircle in the high frequency medium. In the meantime, the resistance related to charge transport at the interface of

ZnO (adsorbed dye) and electrolyte (R2) is what causes the bigger semicircle in the medium frequency medium. The electrolyte and FTO electrode resistances are taken into consideration by the solution resistance (RS). The electron transfer resistance at the interface of the electrolyte, dye, and ZnO electrode is shown by the charge transfer resistance, which is mostly detected in the intermediate frequency region³³.

Fig. 8: EIS spectra of AZO-1%

Table 5: Parameters obtained from EIS studies for AZO- 1%

Sample	Rs (Ω)	R1 (Ω)	R2 (Ω)
AZO – 1%	18.95	4.62	135.89

The data from parameter fitting performed using the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 8 is presented in Table 5. Based on the measurement results, the Rs value obtained is smaller than other ZnO-based DSSC systems⁴⁷. This indicates that a smaller electron transfer resistance will result in an increase in free electrons excited by sunlight, resulting in high conductivity and improved PCE.

4. Conclusion

Al doping on ZnO NRs was successfully carried out via a simple hydrothermal route, which is shown in peak shift (002) with lattice constant compressive strain when Al doping addition shows a decrease in crystal size. AZO-1% showed superior PCE with J_{SC} reaching 25.7 mA/cm². This parameter is supported by a good microstructure with a crystal size of about 53 nm with an optimum aspect ratio of 13.18%. This hexagonal structure helps the absorbance of the ZnO NR layer, resulting in a lower energy gap than the bulk ZnO material itself. Future work that can be done to improve the results of this research is adding a buffer layer to increase wettability and surface area to maximize solar energy conversion and adding mixed dye molecules to the cell.

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Nomenclature

J_{sc}	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)
V_{oc}	Open Circuit Voltage (V)
η	Efficiency (%)
D	Crystal size

Greek Symbols

λ	Wavelength (nm)
θ	Bragg position ($^{\circ}$)
β	FWHM (-)
ν	Frequency (Hz)

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